

Short Communication

OF STRICT

Dibakar Pal

University of Calcutta, Srinath Chakrabarty Lane, Kolkata, India

Corresponding author

Dibakar Pal. University of Calcutta, Srinath Chakrabarty Lane, Kolkata, India

Received: 09 Jan 2025

Accepted : 17 Jan 2025

Published: 22 Jan 2025

Copyright

©2025 Dibakar Pal

OPEN ACCESS

Abstract

A strict person is less romantic. It seems he is not romantic at all. A romantic person is guided by emotion. He is guided by heart. A strict person is guided by motion. He is guided by head. As such a strict person cannot love. He remains unloved. Love does not obey any rule. It is tender in nature. But the paradox is that love breaks all barriers and crosses all boundaries with its violent force. It loves independence. It hates strictness.

Key words: Strict, rule, exact, severe, inflexible, precise, narrow, tight, close, intimate

Introduction

Creative writing is based more on manifestation rather than on expression. It does not inform, rather it reveals. So it bears no reference. The best creative writing is critical, and the best critical writing is creative. This article is an outcome of thinking about creative writing meant for a general readership. As such, I have adopted a free style methodology so that everyone can enjoy the pleasure of reading. As you might know, Francis Bacon (1561-1626), the immortal essayist, wrote many essays namely 'Of Love', 'Of Friendship', 'Of Ambition', 'Of Studies', and so on. The multiple-minded genius correctly pointed out that all the words of the dictionary can be used as themes for essays. But little has been done since his death to continue or finish his monumental task. Bacon's unique individual style of presentation ignited my imagination and encouraged me to write creative essays as a method of relieving a wide range of emotions through catharsis.

ARTICLE

Strict means demanding that rules concerning behaviour are obeyed and observed. For example: My father was very strict.

It is of a person following rules or beliefs exactly e.g., a strict vegetarian.

It is strongly limiting someone's freedom to behave as they wish, or likely to severely punish someone if they do not obey. For example: A strict curfew has been imposed from dusk till dawn.

It is stringent in requirement or control e.g., under strict orders.

It is severe in discipline e.g., a strict teacher.

It is inflexibly maintained or adhered to e.g., strict secrecy.

It is rigorously conforming to principle or a norm or condition.

It is exact. It is precise e.g., in the strict sense of the word.

It is of narrow erect habit of growth e.g., a strict inflorescence.

It is tight. It is close. It is intimate.

Strict is alias and akin to discipline. Discipline makes a nation great. In student life strict discipline is very important. It constructs the back bone of the tender soul. It teaches to raise the head high always. The teacher teaches moral values. In future such a student can face any problem at ease. He becomes an honest person. He does not compromise with any corruption or quality. All these are the outcome of strictness.

A gardener takes care so that a plant can stand erect. Then the grown up tree can face both heat and hail storm. Even the storm cannot uproot it easily. Otherwise the plant falls down and dies. It is equally true in human life also. Mother saves her children with great care and affection. She is very strict in the welfare of her children. For that she is ready to fare well her own peace and happiness. That's why mother is greatest of all.

A student has to bear much pain to realise his aim. He devotes round the clock. All cannot bear that pain. Most of the students become inattentive and ultimately give up studies. This answers why successful students are numbered.

The successful students bear pain in early life. Then rest of the life they enjoy secured peace and happiness. In contrast, the inattentive student who gives up study and enjoys in early life suffers lifelong. He fails successfully in the examination. His successful failure in early life paves the series of failures in his rest part of life. Misfortune dogs him wherever he goes. He suffers till he breathes his last.

To build career strict norms should be followed as sincerely as possible. Only a wise knows it. A fool knows it not.

A child cannot realise the importance of strictness. He becomes absent-minded during his study period. He likes to play. He plays whenever vigilance is less. He finds no interest in studies. This is the drawback of educational system.

The tender soul cannot show anger upon his teacher and parents. As such he is unhappy. Later on when he shines in life then he realises the importance of strictness. Then the established person bows down his head remembering his teachers and parents. He mourns for them who are no more. Tear rolls down through his cheeks.

All do not get guidance. All are not fortunate enough. Further, among them who get guidance very few follow the orders as faithfully as possible. Obey prizes. Disobey punishes.

Man cannot realise the outcome of strict order at the premature stage of life. Man realises its value when he reaches the autumn period of his life. At that belated state of life he cannot compensate his deficiency. He has nothing to do except mourning.

They say mob is brainless crowd. For unruly mob whip is the only way to make them under control. For rational person simple guidance is enough. Here polite request is sufficient. Thus from the status of the persons in question strategy should be fixed. Another school of thought is against any corporal punishment whatever the state and status may be.

There are three types of persons. The first category is strict. He is strict to his policy. He can move but his order will not move. To him word is law. He can give up everything for the sake of his word. But he will not give up word for anything. His policy is crystal clear. He is not tyrant. But the paradox is that he shows tyranny if law is disobeyed. He is transparent. Thus he has conquered allurements. He knows to allure is to sin. And the wage of sin is death.

The second category is flexible. He changes his decision as per situation. His decision varies from person to person, place to place and time to time. He decides something in the morning. He changes his mind in the evening of that very day. Even what he fixes to do right now, he does the other thing or the opposite one in the very next moment. Strictness is against his preference. He finds no glory in strictness. Strictness pains him much. Someone calls him generous. Someone calls him callous. He is ill-famed that he has no locus standee at all. He is loose in his personality trait. However, it seems, he is not detrimental at least.

The third category is a cocktail of both the types. Sometimes he is strict. Sometimes he is flexible. Thus his mood and motive are gloriously so uncertain. He is quite unpredictable. Guess works fails to track his foot prints. As such he is difficult to guess thereby gauge. He is worst of all the three kinds. Then, it seems, strictness is better than flexible. Then the fate can be ascertained with certainty. Vacillation does not persist and causes no tension further. The person, at least, gets relief knowing the severity of strictness or sweetness of flexibility. He takes mental preparation accordingly.

Strictness implies to obey law mechanically. Here romanticism is absent. It is hard reality. Too much of everything is bad. It is equally true in case of strictness or indulgence. Best is the one in between them. Now what is optimum is both a delicate and difficult task. All cannot judge it. It differs from person to person hence the difference among successful and frustrated persons. Success differs. Credit differs. Degrees of failure vary. Degrees of sufferings vary accordingly.

Cite this article: Dibakar Pal. (2025) OF STRICT. *Advanced Educational Research & Reviews* 2 (1): 13-14

The main important thing is that when to be strict and when not to be strict is a difficult task. Only a wise knows it. The fool knows it not. As such the fool is strict when not to be and becomes strict not when it is a must thereby loses both the ways.

Man is not a machine. He cannot be rigid for long. He is basically flexible. He likes to adapt and hopes other will adapt. As such he is afraid of strictness. Strictness has its merit. Childhood can easily be moulded. Strictness at that immature period of life saves from diversion.

Strictness is good when it favours the concerned person. Day light does not help a thief to steal. Then the guards watch strictly. Darkness favours a thief and a culprit for their evil operations.

Similarly, flexible favours someone and may not favour other person simultaneously. Thus both strictness and flexible may or may not be beneficial always. Chance comes once. As such an intelligent person avails of the opportunity.

Honour killing is the worst kind of strictness. So-called honour killer who practices honour killing is well advised to train its members especially its daughters not to involve in love affair which causes life risk. Rather the issues should respect the sentiment of their parents.

Further, the so-called self-proclaimed guardian should know that those days of conservativeness are gone. They cannot be continued in this jet age further. Their age is no longer required. They are simply unwanted. New culture has arrived to control the new generation. As such orthodoxy of any kind is totally invalid now. Rather, the conservative strict person is to punish through honour killing instead.

A strict person may enjoy discretionary power to cope up with the situation. A rule was framed considering the then situation. Time changes. Situation also changes with the change of time. So the old rule does not fit in the new environment. To overcome this stalemate condition the rule maker offered discretionary power to the implementer.

Here a genuine strict person uses his discretionary power to remove the stalemate condition. But a dishonest strict person misuses it. He applies his power to fulfill his own interest or nepotism. Here discredit does not go to discretionary power or rule maker but to the dishonest person. This is like the question, "Is science a blessing or a curse?"

CONCLUSION

A strict person is less romantic. It seems he is not romantic at all. A romantic person is guided by emotion. He is guided by heart. A strict person is guided by motion. He is guided by head. As such a strict person cannot love. He remains unloved. Love does not obey any rule. It is tender in nature. But the paradox is that love breaks all barriers and crosses all boundaries with its violent force. It loves independence. It hates strictness.

REFERENCES

No reference, since the present article is an outcome of Creative Nonfiction Writing.

Copyright: ©2025 **Dibakar Pal**. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.